

The Perspectives Of Students Studying Music In Jordanian Universities Toward Their Field

Subhi Al-Sharqawi

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Abstract

The study aimed to reveal students' perspectives studying music in Jordanian universities toward their field of professional specialization. The study used the descriptive-analytical method to collect data and information on this subject then analyze them. The study's sample comprised 270 male and female music students in Jordanian universities that have the music curriculum of the 2018-2019 academic year. In light of the results, the study recommended that the ones who conduct the teaching role should clarify the crucial part that music plays in all aspects of life, whether emotional, material, or cultural. Also, programs that support and disseminate the musical culture among members of the Jordanian society must be designed and implemented; this is important to make the Jordanian members aware of music and the musical professions and their impact on individual and national incomes.

Introduction

The concept of music teaching is much broader than what can be expressed to signify teaching a range of musical activities. As a subject, music is considered one of the most critical aspects of the school educational process. It aims to take care of the child's complete physical, psychological, emotional, mental, and social development so that he is prepared for life among his community and environment to be a good citizen according to his abilities, readiness, interests, needs, and tendencies through her various educational curricula (Matar et al., 1980).

Cedentop and Thanehill (2000) have emphasized that the teacher's performance and conviction of the roles related to the teaching profession depend on three main aspects: acquiring the information, knowledge, and concepts related to the teaching profession derived from different fields of science, developing the skills and abilities necessary for the preparation and qualification of the teacher, and developing positive perspectives, values and behavior patterns toward the profession.

Renk (1996) has pointed out the need to develop positive perspectives among teachers. He emphasized that a particular profession's positive views play an essential role in energizing the individual toward that profession and motivating him to give and join that profession, and vice versa with the opposing viewpoints. In this regard, he pointed out that the teachers' professional roles require them to develop their positive perspectives and develop their critical mental abilities and be faithful to whatever he is assigned to do in the best possible way.

Perspectives are acquired from being facilitative of behavior prediction as they are reflected in the individual's behavior, speech, and interaction with others. Wade and Tavers (2005) stated that career perspectives are one of the criteria used to predict the social class environment and that the teacher's attitude to his profession depends on his performance, efficiency, and effectiveness in his work. This perspective also affects his students emotionally, socially, and mentally. Wade and Tavers (2005) have also pointed out that teachers' perspectives have a strong and effective impact on their students' attitudes and guidance. This is because the attitude gives the individual's awareness and activities a meaning that helps him accomplish many educational/learning process goals.

Researchers' perceptions of perspectives and their nature have varied. For example, Anderson (2005) has defined an attitude as the desire or willingness of an individual to respond somehow. On the other hand, Allawi (1992) described the perspective as a state of readiness or an invisible implicit tendency mediating between the exciter and the responder that leads the individual to a corrective response to a particular subject, the arousal of sensory or verbal arousal patterns.

It is concluded from the previous definitions that the perspective is a state of readiness or psychological preparation that makes the individual response to a situation or something in some way, ranging from an absolute acceptance to a definite rejection. Although researchers have different views on the concept and nature of perspectives, there is almost a complete agreement that positive perspectives on a particular field or profession play an essential role in motivating the individual toward that area or discipline. There is also a

positive relationship between attitudes that an individual and his action carry, as perspectives play a significant role in the individual's choice of the type of profession they are engaged in (AlMakhzumi, 1995).

The study of perspectives is one of the things that must receive careful attention through the educational process. By studying the extent of attitudes and measuring them, human behavior can be explained, and its positive and negative potentials that will be attested to the reality of the educational community can be predicted. This notion would be followed by planning to confront the indicators that constitute negative perspectives. The analysis of views has become a requirement for the educational process to achieve its objectives more positively and effectively. Therefore, the current study has been developed to investigate music-specialized students' perspectives in Jordanian universities on their field of specialization, including Teaching Music and Musical Education.

Aims of the study

The study aims to identify the perspectives that music-specialized students in Jordanian universities have toward their field, musical teaching, and the impact of gender, GPA, and school year on the students' perspectives.

The problem of the study

Perspectives are generally considered one of the key factors contributing to successful performance in professional fields in general, and in the field of education, in particular. From this point, students' perspectives on music as a specialization (music teaching) and practicing it in the future play a crucial role in their academic achievement and their career or professional performance. After teaching and analyzing the students studying music in Jordanian universities, the researcher has noticed a decreased rate of their cumulative assessments in some of the courses related to their field that they have studied before. From this point on, the study's problem began to crystallize, by which this study is devoted to identifying the perspectives of music-specialized students in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization, as well as tracing the impact of gender, GPA, and the school year on the students' perspectives.

Significance of the study

The significance of the study lies in the following aspects:

- 1- The study acquires its importance from measuring the corresponding perspectives, as the level of student achievement can be expected through the extent of these perspectives. That is, the perspective and the achievement level are correlated.
- 2- The present study may contribute to the identification and positive development of students' perspectives majoring in music for their field of study.
- 3- The study may reveal the most critical factors influencing the formation of students' perspectives on their field of specialization, and thus, may aid in finding the appropriate solutions to deal with them.
- 4- Through the study results, relevant authorities, including officials and faculty members, in the field of music in Jordanian universities may get benefited from the students' perspectives on their major.

Objectives of the study

The current study aims to:

- 1- Determine students' perspectives who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization (music education).
- 2- Determine the influence of the gender variable on the students' attitudes who specialize in music on their area of specialization.
- 3- Determine the impact of the GPA variable on students' perspectives in the field of music on their area of specialization.
- 4- Determine the impact of the school year variable on the perspectives of students who specialize in music on their area of specialization.

Questions of the study

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

- 1- What are the perspectives among students who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization?
- 2- Are there statistically significant differences in the perspectives of students who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization, which are attributable to the gender variable?
- 3- Are there statistically significant differences in the perspectives of students who specialize in music toward their specialization, which is attributable to the GPA variable?
- 4- Are there statistically significant differences in the perspectives of students who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization, which are attributable to the school year variable?

Limitations of the study

This study was conducted in light of the following parameters:

- 1- The study is limited to students who specialize in music in Jordanian universities (Yarmouk University, University of Jordan, Jordanian Academy of Music, National Institute of Music), which grant a bachelor's degree in music.

2- The study results are partially limited by the characteristics of the measuring instrument used in determining the nature of the perspectives of students who specialize in music toward their field of specialization.

3- The study is limited to the first quarter of the school year 2018-2019.

Definition of terms

The following are the occurring terms in the study, which are believed that they should be defined as follows:

- **Perspective:** A state of readiness or preparedness that qualifies an individual to respond to specific behavioral patterns toward particular people, ideas, accidents, situations or things, that constitutes a complicated system in which a wide variety of variables interact within (Wady&Tavers, 2005)

- **The perspective toward music education:** The result of an individual's response to knowledge, concepts, and experiences associated with the music teaching profession somehow makes him work toward this field (procedural definition).

- **The music specialization:** The program that qualifies students to obtain a bachelor's degree in musical education, or music, in Jordanian universities teaching this specialization enables the student, who would become a teacher, able to teach music in the form of a classroom, organizing and managing its activity in its various educational stages.

Theoretical framework and previous studies

First: theoretical framework

The concept of perspectives

Perspectives are regarded as critical components of a teacher's personality. They constitute a realistic component that directs and activates the individual's behavior in situations requiring acceptance or rejection. Wade and Tavers(2005) assume that the perspective is the willingness to respond, meaning that it is not behavior but rather a condition that precedes behavior. Anderson (2005) suggests that the view is what an individual reflects and expresses in harmonious responses with a certain amount of persistence and continuance.

Mawly (1982) has attempted to formulate a comprehensive definition of the perspectives oriented toward the teaching profession, considering these perspectives are the interests or motives that determine an individual's response in a selective manner. In addition to the particular role of attitudes, they can be valuable indicators of maturity development, as perspective patterns are subject to inevitable fluctuations in the several stages of growth in a particular cultural environment.

Perspectives vary in their magnitude, intensity, and vulnerability. An attitude is portrayed as a straight line, with one side representing acceptance and the other representing rejection. In light of this, perspectives can be classified into three main patterns:

- **Positive perspectives:** The acceptance of an individual to a situation or something.

- **Negative perspectives:** The rejection of an individual to a situation or something.

- **Neutral perspectives:** The individual's behavior and options (and his choice) between accepting or rejecting a situation or something (Allawi, 1992).

-Anderson (2005) believes that most of the perspectives have several essential features:

1- Perspectives are acquired, learned but not inherited, and are formed as a result of the experiences of the individual with his or her interaction with the environment.

2- Perspectives imply a special relationship between an individual, an object, or a situation in the environment and reflect the relationship type.

3- Perspectives vary among the individual according to the variation of things or situations.

4- Perspectives are stable and relatively durable but are subject to change and alteration under certain conditions.

5- Perspectives tend to have more individuality than subjectivity among individuals.

6- Perspectives may be private or public, meaning that they may be limited by relating to a position or something general or inclusive.

Most psychologists believe that a perspective consists of three elements (cf. Anderson, 2005; Moole, 1982; Wade&Tavres, 2005):

- The knowledge component: Consists of knowledge, information, and beliefs acquired by the individual, and it has a relationship with the theme of perspective.

- The emotional component: It consists of the individual's feelings about the theme of perspective related to his or her dynamic composition, as they affect an individual's acceptance or rejection of a situation or something.

- The behavioral component: indicates the behavioral patterns that are consistent with the perspective above's features.

Second: Previous studies

Many studies were conducted, whereas there are few studies conducted in the field of music

Al-Kakhen (1993) conducted a study on the motives behind the students' interests in the teaching profession in Saudi Arabia. The objectives of the study were the following:

- 1- Disclosing the type of motives that make students enroll in the education colleges and teacher training institutions for the elementary level in the Kingdom.
- 2- Evaluate the motives that the study will reveal to judge the validity of these motives and their effect on the educational process in general.
3. Give suggestions and recommendations based on the results of the study.

A questionnaire has been used, and it has been applied to 125 students, which consisted of 31 different motives, and the students chose the most important ones. The following question has been asked: What are the main motives that made you join the Teacher Training Institute or the Faculty of Education to become a teacher in the future? An open item was also added so that the student could record the motivation that affected him if it was not among the questionnaire's motives.

The results were as follows:

A) The most important motives are:

- 1- Religion urges the profession of education.
- 2- For the service of the nation.

As for Al-Radaeya (2000), he conducted a study to identify the perspectives of students of the social sciences, at Mu'ta University, toward the field of their specialization. The study aimed to determine the impact of the study variables, including gender, GPA, the educational level, and the interaction between these variables on the students' perspectives. To collect the data, the researcher developed a tool to measure the study of social materials. The most important findings of the study were that most students in the study sample have negative perspectives on their field of specialization. There are also statistically significant differences between the students' perspectives and their GPAs to benefit those with average-and-low-leveled grades. Additionally, there are statistically significant differences between the students' attitudes and their education level for the third- and fourth-year students' benefit. Results showed that there are no differences between the perspectives of females and males toward social studies.

The study of Alamayreh (2004) has examined students' attitudes College of Education in Jordan toward their area of specialization, the education profession. The study explored whether or not there is an impact of the variables of gender and level of education. A questionnaire consisting of (47) paragraphs divided into three main groups has been used. The study's sample has been limited to students in their first and fourth year of university only, and it was comprised of (183) students. The results of the study indicated that the perspectives of students are somewhat positive toward the teaching profession. The results also showed no statistically significant differences in the students' perspectives on the teaching profession due to the variables of gender and level of education. Kadhim and Al-Namari (2004) conducted a study aiming at identifying the perspectives of Sultan Qaboos University's students toward the field of psychology, and the extent of contribution of variables like gender, age, specialization, GPA, and studying psychological courses on the perspective toward the field of psychology. A research tool consisting of (58) paragraphs has been developed to achieve this, and it was applied on (260) students from the various colleges of Sultan Qaboos University. The study's results indicated that there are positive perspectives on psychology, and there are statistically significant differences in the students' attitudes with regards to students who took psychology courses. Nevertheless, results have indicated no differences like the student perspective according to the variables of gender, age, specialization, and GPA.

Foreign-language studies

In a study aiming to figure the impact of experience and good preparation in altering the perspectives of elementary school music teachers, Lawries (1998) has found that they need pure information to form a clear idea of the profession of education. The new teachers who have positive perspectives and preparation skills will be on the right path to success in their first year of work. This study was written for music teachers during their first year of teaching, and the primary goal of this study was revolving around perspective and preparation.

Hill's (1999) study has also aimed at examining how teachers can be developed and become committed as their perspectives and beliefs are changing through their participation in the Professional Development Arts Integration Program.

This study has been designed to:

- 1- Employ the perspectives and beliefs of the examined teachers during the Professional Development Arts Integration Program.
- 2- Employ the perspectives and beliefs of the examined teachers through the Professional Development Arts Integration Program.
- 3- Defining the perspectives and beliefs according to the program's framework.

The study has revealed that altering the perspective and the belief was low and occurred on special occasions, and it occupied a place in advanced stages. The change in the attitudes and views of the examined ones is highly linked to the curriculum and the teaching compared to perspectives and beliefs revolving around teaching specialization.

Maney (2000) studied students' perspectives at the Faculty of Education in sports and health education. The sample included (170) students from the Faculty of Education. The data has been collected using a specially

built measuring tool to measure the study's objective. The results showed that there were positive perspectives for the students of the Faculty of Education toward teaching sports and health education. The results also showed statistically significant differences in students' attitudes according to the GPA in favor of high- and middle-level students.

On the other hand, Mills (2004) has studied university students' perspectives toward statistics education in an attempt to understand whether there was an impact of variables like previous experience, competency, and gender on the students' attitudes. To accomplish the aim of the study, a Lickert rating measure, and the sample included (203) university students in the United States. The study results indicated that perspectives on the field of statistics are negative, and the results showed that there are statistically significant differences in the student's perspectives on the teaching of statistics due to the variables of experience, competence, and gender.

It was found that there are some similarities between a few of the studies in many aspects. Nevertheless, there are also differences between them in other areas, as it is noticed that the results between all studies using university students as their sample.

Analyzing the literature review reveals that some of the studies have indicated the positive perspectives among learners toward their specializations. On the other hand, some other studies highlighted the negative views on these specializations. This discrepancy seems to be due to the differences among the target society, sample, and the methods used to study perspectives. It is also noted that the results of these studies have not been decisive in determining the impact of the variables of gender GPA/level of achievement on perspectives. Some studies have indicated a relationship between the GPA/level of achievement and the view's nature. Alternatively, other studies did not imply such an association. Finally, some studies have shown that males' positive perspectives surpass females, while others have demonstrated adverse results.

A review of previous studies shows an apparent scarcity of Arab and local studies on the study of university students' perspectives toward the field of music specialization. The current study is distinguished from other studies by it considering multiple variables to be analyzed. The studies' variables consisted of altering the nature of perspectives on the field of music, as the dependent variable, and the variables of gender, GPA, and school year, as the independent variables.

The current study is similar to previous studies in terms of some procedures used in designing the study's curriculum and dealing with its variables, and measuring some variables. The study has benefited from the literature review analyzed and mentioned in the related studies containing a similar subject

Methodology

A descriptive approach has been used in collecting the student's perspectives as it fits the nature of the current study.

The population of the study

The study sample is comprised of (270) male and female students who are registered in the first semester of the 2018-2019 academic year. The original population has been recruited using the Department of Admission and Registration's official records and documents in three Jordanian universities.

Sample of the study

The study sample included a total of (200) students who were randomly selected to ensure that the sample is collective and representative. According to the school year variable, the population has been divided into four main groups (first, second, third, fourth). A total of (190) male and female students have responded to the questionnaire, with 95% of the 200 students' total questionnaires answered. After the exclusion of the ten questionnaires that have missing information, the final sample of the study became (180) students, (60: 33.33%) of who are males and (120: 66.66%) are females. The tables listed as (1) and (2) indicate the classification of the sample members.

Table 1: The classification of the sample members according to gender and school year

School Year	Gender		Total
	Males	Females	
First-year	15	20	45
Second-year	15	20	45
Third-year	15	20	45
Fourth-year	15	20	45
Total	60	120	180

Table 2: The classification of the sample members according to the GPA

GPA	Number	Percentage
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2.49 - 2.00	60	33%
2.99 - 2.50	72	40%
3.49 - 3.00	30	17%
3.99 - 3.50	18	10%
	180	100%

The tool of the study

To achieve the study's goals and to answer its questions, a special tool was designed to measure the students' perspectives on music. A careful analysis of the related literature, studies, and resources related to the study's topic and research methods has been conducted. Based on the review of the previous literature, research, and studies on education, the dimensions in which the study's tool can be used have been specified, and they are four. Based on the effects of the study tool's four main dimensions, the researcher began to build and identify its paragraphs. In the initial version of the instrument, a total of (55) paragraphs have been used distributed across the four main dimensions.

The tool was presented to a group of specialized referees from the Department of Psychology, Curricula, Teaching Methods, and Musical Education at the Faculty of Fine Arts at the University of Yarmouk and the College of Design and Arts at the University of Jordan to verify its accuracy. Following the revision of the tool based on the proposals of the arbitrators, the instrument contained in its final form (45) paragraphs (25) of which were worded positively, (20) other paragraphs were worded negatively. The tool's paragraphs have been distributed in three dimensions in the following order:

Dimension one: Perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music, including (13) paragraphs.

Dimension two: Perspectives on music as course material, including (8) paragraphs.

Dimension three: Perspectives on music as a professional field, including (11) paragraphs.

Dimension four: Perspectives on the importance of music, including (11) paragraphs.

In designing the tool, Lickert's Scale of Estimation has been resorted to, where next of each paragraph, a scale of five degrees has been placed: I strongly agree(5), I agree(4), I am unsure(3), I do not agree(2), I strongly do not agree(1), (See Appendix 1).

According to the tool's (45) paragraphs and the response levels of each paragraph from (1 to 5), the theoretical extent of the tool's level ranges from a minimum of (45) to a maximum of (225). The total score for each student was considered an indication of the extent of the increase or decrease in perspective toward musical education. The digital value of the neutral response is equal to 3 degrees; each student who scored (135) points, meaning (60% and above) which is equivalent to an average of (3.00 and above) has been considered to have a positive perspective. Nevertheless, each student receiving less than (135) points, with (less than 60%) which is equivalent to an average of (less than 3.00) has been considered to have a negative perspective.

The validity of the tool

The tool has been validated by:

First: Virtual Honesty / Arbitrators

The researcher verified the apparent truthfulness of the performance dimensions and their main dimensions through presenting the initial draft of the tool to eight specialized judges from the teaching staff of the departments of psychology, curricula and teaching methods, and the musical education at the Faculty of Education at Yarmouk University and the University of Jordan. They were asked to judge the tool in terms of whether it was authentic enough to measure the study's goals. To determine how relevant the paragraph was to the theme it has been assigned to and trace how precise the paragraphs were and how valid they were to be applied. The judges were asked to add any suggested points to modify the wording of any item.

After collecting the questionnaire and observing the judges' notes, their observations and recommendations, which provided the researcher with feedback on the wording of some paragraphs and their suitability for the objectives of the study and their affiliation with the dimension in which they are included, have been taken into account. A suggestion of limiting the number of paragraphs to (45) distributed to four dimensions has also been taken into account. The tool was then presented in its final form to the same arbitrators with an average agreement rate of (89%), which indicates that the tool has a high degree of apparent sincerity.

Second: Inner integrity

The validation of the tool has also been verified by calculating the tool's internal homogeneity. The internal integrity is measured by calculating the correlation factors for each dimension in correlation with the tool's primary domain. The analysis results showed that all correlation factors between tool dimensions were homogeneous, indicating that the instrument had a high degree of inner integrity. Table 3 illustrates this as follows:

Table 3: The inner integrity coefficient between the degree of each tool dimension and the overall tool score

Dimension	Number of paragraphs	Significance
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Perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music	13	0.01
Perspectives on music as a course material	8	0.01
Perspectives on music as a professional field	13	0.01
Perspectives on the importance of music	11	0.01

Tool stability: The following methods have been used:

First: consistent stability: The tool's stability was calculated by the re-application (test rate), where it was applied to (15) students not included in the study's sample count. The tool has been reapplied to the same group of students after (14) days, and the Pearson correlation coefficient between the first and second applications was calculated. By calculating the stability coefficient for each of the four tool dimensions; which ranged from (0.78 to 0.85), the tool's total stability coefficient, which was (0.82), has been calculated, and it is concluded that this stability coefficient indicates good tool stability (See Table 4).

Table 4: Stability coefficient for the dimensions and the overall questionnaire gradient

Dimension	Number of paragraphs	Stability coefficient
Perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music	13	.78
Attitudes on music as a course material	8	.82
Attitudes on music as a professional field	13	.82
Attitudes on the importance of music	11	.85
Overall correlation coefficient	45	.82

Second: Stability of internal consistency

The tool's stability has also been calculated by calculating the Alpha Cronbach stability coefficient for calculating internal consistency. The Alpha parameters ranged from (0.82) to (0.86). Afterward, the tool's total alpha stability coefficient has been calculated, and it was (0.81). It is then indicated that these correlation values of internal consistency stability are high, and table (5) illustrates this.

Table 5: Stability coefficient for the tool's dimensions and the overall tool degree

Dimension	Number of paragraphs	Stability coefficient
Perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music	13	.80
Attitudes on music as a course material	8	.79
Attitudes on music as a professional field	13	.83
Attitudes on the importance of music	11	.81
Overall correlation coefficient	45	.81

Statistical methods

To conduct the study and to answer the statistical questions of the study, the following statistical methods have been considered:

- 1- Using the Pearson correlation coefficient to calculate the internal homogeneity and the stability coefficient and the Alpha factor of Cronbach to calculate the internal consistency.
- 2- Calculating the percentages and occurrences, arithmetic averages, and grades to answer the study's first question.
- 3- Using the t-test to answer the study's second question.
- 4- Using the ANOVA test to answer the study's third and fourth questions.

Results

The following dimension contains a review of the study's results based on the order of the study's questions.

The first question: What are the perspectives among students who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization?

Means, standard deviation, and percentages have been calculated for all tool dimensions and their items. Table (6) summarizes the results.

Table 6: The arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and percentage of students' responses for each dimension and paragraph attested and for the tool as a whole

Dimension	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Percentage
Perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music	3.58	.54	71.60
Perspectives on music as a course material	3.74	.62	74.80
Perspectives on music as a professional field	3.92	.57	78.40
Perspectives on the importance of music	3.54	.44	70.80
Overall correlation coefficient	3.60	.54	73.90

Table (6) indicates that the calculated notions have varied in their arithmetic averages and percentages. The students' perspectives have ranged from (3.54) to (3.92), i.e., equivalent to rates of (70.80%) to (78.40%). Regarding the standard deviation, the students' perspectives have SDs ranging from (0.44) to (0.57). The students' attitudes mean was (73.90%) and a standard deviation (0.54). The dimension of music perspectives as a professional field has been ranked first, followed by the dimension of the attitude toward music as a course material ranking second, then, the attitude toward the scientific knowledge of music came in third place. Finally, the perspective toward the importance of music has been ranked fourth. According to the study's standards, the results indicate that students studying music in Jordanian universities are positive toward their field.

The second question: Are there statistically significant differences in the perspectives of students who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization attributable to the gender variable?

Means and standard deviations were calculated, and a t-test has been used to test the differences between the student perspectives' according to gender variable. Table (7) illustrates these results.

Table 7: Means, standard deviation, t-value, and its significance for the students' responses according to the gender variable

Dimension	Male students		Female students		T-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music	3.44	.42	3.72	.58	2.86*
Perspectives on music as a course material	3.52	.45	3.96	.59	3.23*
Perspectives on music as a professional field	3.70	.51	4.14	.61	3.45*
Perspectives on the importance of music	3.32	.51	3.77	.53	2.02
Overall correlation coefficient	3.49	.47	3.89	.57	2.89*

*T-value at 0.05=2.08.

The results of table (7) indicate that there are statistically significant differences at the alpha significance level of (0.05) in the averages of the students' perspectives on their area of specialization, due to the gender variable, with regards to female students, in the dimension of views on the scientific knowledge of music, perspectives on music as course material, perspectives on music as a professional field with t-values of (2.86), (3.23), (3.45) and (2.89) respectively. Those t-values are considered to be significant at the alpha significance level (.05). As for perspectives on the importance of music, the results show no statistically significant differences in student perspectives according to the gender variable.

The third question is: Are there statistically significant differences in students' perspectives who specialize in music toward their specialization attributable to the GPA variable?

According to the GPA variable, the one-Way ANOVA test was used to examine the differences between the mean values of the students' perspectives. Table (8) demonstrates the results.

Table 8: ANOVA test results and the F-value of the students' responses according to the GPA variable

Dimension	Variances	Sum Squares	of Degree of Freedom	Mean Squares	of F-value
Perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music	Across groups	248.00	3	124.00	*4.69
	Within groups	8642.00	177	140.05	
	Total	8890.0	180		
Perspectives on music as a course material	Across groups	182.71	3	115.12	*3.56
	Within groups	7659.48	177	214.32	
	Total	7842.19	180		
Perspectives on music as a professional field	Across groups	228.40	3	95.26	*5.41
	Between groups	7725.21	177	102.45	
	Total	7953.61	180		
Perspectives on the importance of music	Across groups	306.24	3	91.85	*1.74
	Between groups	5545.42	177	115.36	
	Total	5851.66	180		
Total	Across groups	965.35	3	222.66	*5.98
	Between groups	2957.11	177	1424.25	
	Total	3922.46	180		

Table 8 shows that there are statistically significant differences at the alpha significance level between the mean values of the students' perspectives due to the GPA variable in the dimensions: perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music, attitudes on music as a subject, views on music as course material, and the perspectives on music as a professional field. Besides, the f-values of the dimensions above are (4.69), (3.56), (5.41), (5.98), respectively. The f-values are statistically significant at the alpha significance level (.05). As for the perspective on the importance of music, the results showed no statistically significant differences in student perspectives according to the GPA variable.

Scheffe test was used to compare all the dimensions that showed the statistical differences, and table 9 shows these results.

Table 9: The results of a Scheffe test for the dimensional comparisons and their significance levels according to the GPA variable

Dimension	GPA	Mean	2.00-2.49	2.49-3.00	3.00-3.49	3.50-3.99
Perspectives	2.00-2.49	3.21	-	-	-	

on the scientific knowledge of music	2.49-3.00	3.45	1.45	-	-	
	3.00-3.49	3.92	*3.71	*3.69	-	
	3.50-3.99	4.14	*5.12	4.87	*3.24	
Perspectives on music as a course material	2.00-2.49	3.54	-	-		
	2.49-3.00	3.72	1.88	-		
	3.00-3.49	3.98	*3.71	1.91		
	3.50-3.99	4.08	*5.02	*4.51	2.12	
Perspectives on music as a professional field	2.00-2.49	3.28	-	-		
	2.49-3.00	3.51	2.05	-		
	3.00-3.49	3.88	*3.89	*3.61		
	3.50-3.99	4.01	*4.92	*4.87	2.41	
The field as a whole	2.00-2.49	3.65	-	-		
	2.49-3.00	3.75	2.05	-		
	3.00-3.49	3.94	*3.27	2.31		
	3.50-3.99	4.30	*4.45	*4.10	*3.42	

Table (9) shows statistically significant differences between the mean values of students' perspectives in the dimension of the perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music in favor of students with a GPA of (3.50 to 3.99). Scheffe's test results indicate the statistically significant differences between the students' mean values of perspectives in favor of students with a GPA score of (3.00 to 3.49).

The results of table (9) designate statistically significant differences between the mean values of the perspectives of students with GPA scores of (2.00 to 2.49), (2.50 to 2.99), and (3.50 to 3.99) toward the dimension of music as course material. Additionally, there are statistically significant differences between the mean values of students' perspective in favor of the students with a GPA score of (3.00 to 3.49).

Moreover, results showed significant differences in the students' perspectives in favor of the students' GPA of (3.50 to 3.99). There are statistically significant differences in the mean values of the attitudes in favor of students with GPA scores (3.00 to 3.49).

Furthermore, there are statistically significant differences in the students' perspectives in favor of the students with GPA scores (3.50 to 3.99). Correspondingly, Scheffe's test results approve that there are statistical differences in the mean values of perspectives of students with GPA scores of (2.00 to 2.49) and (3.00 to 3.49), with the latter being more significant.

The fourth question: Are there statistically significant differences in the perspectives of students who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization attributable to the school year variable?

One-Way ANOVA test was used to examine the differences between the mean values of the students' perspectives on their area of specialization for each tool dimension and the tool as a whole according to the school year variable. The below table summarizes the statistical results.

Table 10: One-way ANOVA test results and the F values of the student responses for the tool's dimensions and the tool as a whole according to the school year variable

Dimension	Variances	Sum Squares	of	Degree of Freedom	of	Mean Squares	of	F-value
Perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music	Across groups	264.00		3		110.04		*1.61
	Within groups	5522.00		177		119.11		
	Total	5786.0		180		-		

Perspectives on music as a course material	Across groups	176.41	3	98.54	*3.84
	Within groups	6471.25	177	177.71	
	Total	6647.66	180	-	
Perspectives on music as a professional field	Across groups	210.40	3	101.25	*5.04
	Between groups	6154.21	177	141.45	
	Total	6334.61	180	-	
Perspectives on the importance of music	Across groups	345.27	3	79.62	1.62
	Between groups	4123.42	177	100.26	
	Total	4468.69	180	-	
Total	Across groups	872.81	3	201.445	*4.21
	Between groups	2472.42	177	1342.32	
	Total	3345.23	180	-	

Table (10) demonstrates, there are statistically significant differences at the alpha significance level (0.05) between the mean values of the students' perspectives on music as a course material due to the school year variable in two dimensions: music as course material, and as course material in addition to the total dimensional count. The attested F-values are recorded as (3.84), (5.04), and (4.21) for the dimensions and the total count, respectively. All the F-values above are regarded as significant at the alpha significance level, .05. As for the dimensions of perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music and views on the importance of music, the results show no statistically significant differences in student perspectives according to the school year.

To disclose the source of the statistical differences in the variable of school years, a Scheffe-Test was used for the dimensional comparisons of all the statistical differences, and table (11) shows these results.

Table (11) proves statistically significant differences in the mean values of the first, second, third, and fourth-year students' perspectives. Scheffe's test results also indicate the statistically significant differences in the mean values of the perspectives of first, second, and third-year students, with the third-year students' results being more significant.

Moreover, and regarding the perspectives of students toward musical education as a professional area, it is clear from the table (11) that there are statistically significant differences between the mean values of the perspectives of the first, second, third, and fourth-year student in favor of the fourth-year students. Correspondingly, Scheffe's test results show statistically significant differences in the mean values of the first, second, and third-year students' perspectives, with the third-year students having the most significant results.

Finally, there are statistically significant differences in the mean values of first, second, third, and fourth-year students toward the total count of dimensions of the tool and for the instrument as a whole in favor of the fourth-year students. It is also shown that there are statistically significant differences in the mean values of perspectives of the first, second, and third-year students, with the latter being the most significant.

Table 11: The results of Scheffe's Test for the dimensional comparisons and their significance of the mean values of the tool's dimensions as a whole according to the school year variable

Dimension	School year	Mean	R	Second-year	Third-year	Fourth-year
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Perspectives on music as a course material	First-year	3.32	-			
	Second-year	3.65	2.01	-		
	Third-year	3.78	*3.46	2.71	-	
	Fourth-year	3.98	*5.12	*4.24	2.12	-
Perspectives on music as a professional field	First-year	3.42	-			
	Second-year	3.49	2.13	-		
	Third-year	3.74	*3.65	2.56	-	
	Fourth-year	3.98	*4.83	*4.76	2.18	-1
Total	First-year	3.47	-			
	Second-year	3.55	2.25	-		
	Third-year	3.87	*3.80	2.45	-	
	Fourth-year	4.00	*4.20	*3.80	2.30	-

Discussion

The study aimed to investigate students' perspectives majoring in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization. It also sought to determine the impact of gender, GPA, and the school year on the students' perspectives. The study results showed a positive attitude among students who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization. The mean value of the tool's total count of the students' perspectives is (3.69), which is equivalent to (73.90%), which exceeds the theoretical mean value on the scale, which is equal to (3.00) that is equivalent to (60%). Such results are attributed to many factors, most important of which are: the continuing need of the educational labor market for specialists in the field of music education, the availability of opportunities for work in public and private schools, and the desire of students to study music, and the student awareness to the importance of the field of music specialization and its connection with several other areas.

The increase of the positive student perspective of music students toward their field of specialization can also be attributed to the acceptance policy for music, which is based on several criteria, most notable of which is the students' performance test. This has contributed to a large extent to rationalizing the number of those admitted to music departments in Jordanian universities and selecting the best among them who enjoy positive perspectives on the field of music.

The study results are in line with Maney's (2000) study that proved that there are positive perspectives of the Faculty of Education students toward the field of physical education, considering that it is the closest previous study to the current one. Nevertheless, these results of AlRawadyeh (2000) showed that the perspectives of students who specialize in the fields of social sciences at Mutah University were hostile toward their area of specialization.

With regards to the differences in perspectives on their area of specialization according to gender variable, the results indicated statistically significant differences in each of the following dimensions: perspectives on the scientific knowledge of music, views on music as course material, perspectives on music as a professional field, in addition to the total count of dimensions in favor of the female students. Thus, this shows that female students have more optimistic perspectives on music specialization than male students. As for the views on the importance of music, the results illustrated that there are no statistically significant differences in the student perspectives according to the gender variable, which can be mainly attributed to the need of the job market for more female teachers than male teachers in the music field, and that the job opportunities for females are higher than the ones for males.

This can also be led back to the fact that female students can sense the local market's need for music specialization. Moreover, female students and their parents are aware enough of this profession's high level of satisfaction regarding life requirements, especially the females who feel that the income they earn from this

profession meets their life needs. Additionally, this is due to the media's role in highlighting the importance of musical education and its direct impact on females more than males.

In analyzing the individual differences in the student perspectives on their field of specialization according to the GPA variable, the results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the student perspectives in the dimensions of the views on the scientific knowledge of music, perspectives on music as course material, perspectives on music as a professional field, in addition to the total count of dimensions in favor of students with high and average GPA scores. It is consistent with the relationship between perspectives and achievement that the educational literature emphasizes, by which there is a direct connection between the student perspectives and their academic achievements. This means that as the students' information study experience and GPA increase, their views on their specialization will be deeper.

The results of the current study, which found a positive increase in the perspectives of students with high GPA scores toward their field of specialization, are in line with the findings of Milles's (2004) study, which indicated that an increase in the GPA scores could increase the positive perspectives of students toward their field of specialization. The study of Maney (2000) also suggested that intensive academic expertise could improve the student perspectives on their specialization field. However, the current study results are inconsistent with those of AlRawadyeh's (2000) study, which indicated statistically significant differences between the student perspectives and their levels of achievement in favor of those with intermediate and lower GPA scores.

The results proved that there are statistically significant differences due to the school year variable in the following dimensions: perspectives on music as course material, perspectives on music as a professional field, and the total count of dimensions in favor of the third-fourth years' students. It has been attested that students in their fourth year have higher positive perspectives on their specialization field. This proposition is consistent with the hypothesis that the educational literature discusses, mentioning that as the school year increases, the positive attitudes on a certain field of specialization also increase. This result can be attributed to the experiences and information that the students learned during their school years, which have contributed to students' positive perspectives in their advanced years, especially in the fourth year. This finding may also be explained by the fact that the third- and fourth-year students are the most mature and capable of understanding the perspective's content, thus judging it.

In general, the results of this study are consistent with the case of AlRawadyeh's (2000) study, in which he found statistically significant differences in the student perspectives on their field of specialization in favor of the third- and fourth-year students, despite the different themes of the tool used.

Conclusion

In light of the results of the study, the following notions were concluded:

1. There is a positive perspective among students who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their specialization.
2. There are statistically significant differences in the students' perspectives on their specialization area due to the GPA variable, especially those with high and medium GPA scores.
3. There are statistically significant differences in the students' perspectives on their area of specialization due to the school year variable in favor of the students in the third and fourth years.

Therefore, this study's results were partly consistent with the results of some earlier studies and contrary to some others.

Recommendations

In light of the study's results, which showed that students in Jordanian universities have a positive perspective toward their field of music, the researcher proposed the following recommendations:

- 1- members of the teaching staff in Jordanian universities are urged to develop positive perspectives, values and behavior patterns among music students toward their specific field of specialization and the general profession.
- 2- Conduct further studies to identify the factors and reasons for the relationship between the school year and students' positive perspectives toward the field of specialization.
- 3- Conduct in-depth studies examining the reasons for the weak positive perspective toward the field of music among males when compared with females
- 4- Conduct further studies to reveal the nature of students' perspectives who specialize in music in Jordanian universities toward their field of specialization.

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Author Information

Dr. Subhi Al-Sharqawi

Associate Professor, Hashemite University, Faculty
of Educational Sciences
